

EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION LED INITIATIVES IN TEACHERS' CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ON LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN KINIHIRA AND TUMBA SECTORS, RULINDO DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to examine the relationship between continuous professional development (CPD) on learners' academic performance in Rwandan primary schools. This focused on the following specific objectives: What is the relationship between Teacher in-service training and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools, To what extent teacher peer learning platforms relate to learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools, What is the relationship between teacher coaching and mentoring and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools. The descriptive research design was used. Quantitative and qualitative approaches were used to analyze data. 158 people was used as target population and 103 as simple size to represent the whole population. Data were collected using structured questions with 5-point Likert scales and an interview. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, standard deviation, means, and regression analysis while qualitative data were analyzed using thematic method that helped in analyzing qualitative data. The finding from study concluded that there significant relationship continuous professional development and learners' academic performance in Rwandan primary schools. SPSS and Thematic method were used to calculate regression analysis of the study: Basing the findings from the study, the researchers revealed that there some gaps which need to be solved by different organs such, Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) across the world. The results indicated that there is positive and significant effect of teacher coaching and mentoring on learners' academic performance ($B=0.894$, P value >0.00). The study recommended to provide frequent continuous professional development in

schools across the country. The study recommend REB to do a survey on how continuous professional development (CPD) impacting the quality of education. In the same regard, the study recommend the all educational related Stakeholders to fund continuous professional development to teaching and administrative staff.

Keywords: Continuous Professional Development, learners, academic performance.

1.INTRODUCTION

For education to become very successful and answer what it intends to solve and build the capacity of the people together with their welfare, it must meet specific standards. Others factors, it is deeply recommended that universal objective planned for education in terms of having accessibility to the quality of education, all of these oblige teachers to be experienced, qualified and trained to perform assigned tasks effectively (TGE, 1994).

As pass many years in teaching, it is also the ways an experience increases every years. In teaching and learning career, comprises but no become an obstacle to the curriculum reforms (Loucks & Pratt, 1979). For letting them and empower in the abilities to put into practice new curriculum, most of the teachers should be engaged in continuous professional development which can be a bridge to the teachers to adopt the new change which was made in curriculum (Bredeson, 2002). Many researchers in different literatures and writings used many terms to define or to give the meaning of continuous professional development which include teachers in service training, personnel development, progressive education, training and self-development or self-teaching and learning. In educational institutions, there are many different type of learning activities and school administrators.

Continuous professional development is taken as the way of linking the gap between teachers' development and the demand for an institutional change (Birman, Desimone, Porter & Garet, 2000). But most of these professional development activities are not capable of helping the improvement of the opportunity for change to become accurate or effective.

The review of the writing revealed that there is a permanent investigation of the scholars to examine the problem of professional development by trying to explore what should be done to improve the effectiveness of professional development. Many researchers such as Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) continued to define effective professional development as structured professional learning that results in changes in teacher practices and improvements in student learning outcomes.

Academicicians examine the effectiveness of continuous professional development in terms of categories, indicators and factors that can influence the effectiveness of professional development

(Birman, 2000; Hunzicker, 2011; Hough, 2011; Desimone, 2011; Gibson et al. 2012; Bayar, 2014; and Abu-Tineh et al. 2018). According to UNESCO (2003), Professional development in a broad sense, refers to the development of a person in his or her professional role. Continuous professional development widely is defined as the improvement of an individual in this or her professional duties (UNESCO, 2003). More precisely, teacher development is the professional development that a teacher attains as an impact of getting new experience and improving his/ her teaching systematically.

Continuous professional development comprises current experience (like participating in workshops and professional conferences and meetings, monitoring and field visits and so on) and informal experience which include reading publications related to the career, watching documentaries movies which correspond with professionalism (Ganser, 2000). Continuous professional development can happen in many different ways: permanent school day at school, but before teaching and learning starts or later after the time teachers get call the day school staff can plan to provide professional development to the teachers or during the summer and others school holidays (Mizell, 2010).

The terms of professional development, is wider than career improvement which is explained as the change that happens as a teacher passes through the professional vocation cycle (Sysko, 2018). And wider than staff improvement, which is giving of organized in-service curricula planned to empower the improvement of pairs of teachers; it is the only one of the gradual interventions that must be utilized for teachers professional development (Glatthorn, 1995, p. 41).

Once a person emphasizes on professional development, one can analyze the accuracy of experience, the way in which professional development be done, and the process in which it will be implemented (Ganser, 2000; Fielding and Schalock, 1985). Teachers professional development can bring a difference to the students' performance depending on kind of program undertaken and help that is being given. Precise factors such as the years of attending training(in service training, teachers fluency in instructional language, mastering of the content, having teaching facilities such books and materials and having the capacity of using those materials, teachers expectation on learners academic performance, time allocated to the classroom preparation of pedagogical

documents, monitoring and evaluating students achievement and provision of feedback, all of these have been highlighted as factors which influence the quality of students and teachers performance.

Many reviews which were made revealed that was no specific or single meaning of professional development. According to Speck, B. W. (2001), Professional development is a lifelong collaborative learning process that nourishes the growth of educators both as individuals and as team members to improve their abilities and skills". Bredeson (2002), in his definition, highlighted three interdependent concepts (learning, engagement, and improved practices), and he defined PD "as learning opportunities that engage educators' creative and reflective capacities in the way that strengthens their practice.

Training is a kind of professional development where beneficiaries attend the lecturing of workshop-categories (Austin, Marini & Croteau, 2005). Training gather the trainees in a non-active role, for examples because an expert in given discipline transmit the contents to the teachers focus on the planned activities in daily agenda, this strategy ensures that teachers must change their attitudes and values to learn (Sparks & Loucks-Horsley,1989).

According to Joyce and Shower (1988), someone has to decide what will be the substance of training, which will provide training, when and where the training will be held and for what duration. Training "can be short and/or long term; it is cost-effective as it can target more teachers in one place with a small number of trainers using materials that can be reused with other cohorts" (Al-Ghatrifi, 2016). Monitoring is among the ways of professional development programs for teachers that is commonly part of training new teachers in the schools in the activities called induction. According to Allen & Casbergue, 1997).

According to Flynn, Lissy, Alicea, Tazartes and McKay (2016) it was confirmed that mentoring activities benefit the mentees also the mentoring activities benefit the mentors and schools themselves in many ways. For the mentees the activities give them confidence and professionalism in their career and even support them pedagogically and psychologically and for the school academic performance increase in school based exams, district and at national level.

In Rwandan perspectives, this research put emphasis on understanding the element that can influence the effectiveness of continuous professional development of teachers in Rwanda.

In Rwanda education, a well -trained teacher is considered as milestone which contributes to the development of teaching and learning processes, leading to quality of education (MINEDUC, 2007).

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nowadays, vision and mission of ministry of education "to provide the citizens of Rwanda with equal opportunities to high-quality education through the world-class learning facilities and renowned learning institution "(MINEDUC, 2012). Makunja (2016) competency based curriculum is a sort of education system which wants to improve students' capability to study and perform better to the standardized level. The elaboration of competency based curriculum come on right time because the internal and external jobs markets is obliging to move from traditional teaching approaches to competency based curriculum. In addition to that government has to make sure that the skills, knowledge, attitudes and value given to Rwandans in education are meeting with the change at global markets in 21st century" (REB, 2016).

With a target of strengthening teachers, schools' administrators and making sure that the implementation of new curriculum in 2016 is effective. Rwanda Education board elaborated continuous professional development at national level. Before 2016, continuous professional development was not the thing which was known in education system of Rwanda, it was not easy to make CPD in Rwandan schools. Upon the introduction of competency based curriculum, most of schools and institutions started providing continuous professional development to their employees so that they can update their knowledge and skills, these were used as the ways of making effective implementation of competency based curriculum . It is very important to engage teachers in CPD so that the implementation of competence based curriculum can be effective (Bredeson, 2002; Gibson & Brooks, 2012). However, many schools do not get the opportunity to give their teachers CPD; and if this continue, the implementation of new curriculum won't be successful and academic performance cannot be achieved. In addition to this, school graduates will be incompetent at the labor markets.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- (i) What is the relationship between Teacher in-service training and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools?
- (ii) To what extent does teacher peer learning platforms relate to learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools?
- (iii) What is the relationship between teacher coaching and mentoring and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools?

1.4. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- (i) To examine the relationship between Teacher in-service training and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools.
- (ii) To identify the relationship between Teacher peer learning platforms and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools.
- (iii) To Analyze the relationship between teacher coaching and mentoring, and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Teachers in service training and learners' academic performance

According to Mizell (2010), when the teachers are engaged in service training, it means that it is formal process of educating people by using conference, seminars, workshop and field trip and cooperative among the team at university and college. However, in –service training one can include informal teaching like discussions among work colleagues, personal research and study, observation of workmate works and other kind of peer learning.

People use many others terms while explaining professional development, they use staff professional development, teachers training, professional learning among others. But however, one

can call it, the meaning is always the same and the purpose is the same, there is no doubt that continuous professional development provides significant impact on learning achievement.

Many other researchers such as Casteel and Ballantyne (2010) indicated that professional development can be related to the measurable achievement in learners' academic performance and discipline of learners. Students' achievement can be the best determinants of the types of continuous professional development provided to the teachers and it can determine how that training is effective to the beneficiaries. Teachers in service training is an obligation for new hired and experienced teachers because education system is dynamic means that there are always great change in policy making, curriculum development, policies which should be taught.

Different studies have discovered that in service training have significant impact on learners' academic performance in educational institutions. Rahman, Jumani, Akhter, Chisthi & Ajmal, (2011) studied about the relationship between in service teachers training and effective teachers and come up with possible solution which are follows, the conclusion was that in service teachers training has positive relationship with effective classroom teaching and correlation showed that the positive relationship between learners' academic performance and teachers training.

In many researches, professional development was linked with partnership and students' performance, researchers like Sullivan (2008) from quantitative research concluded that one teachers participate in professional development students' academic performance increases too because of the skills and knowledge that teachers acquired from trainings. Many studies about professional development conducted, teachers were asked how continuous professional development impacted on students' learners' academic performance by describing the effectiveness of professional development to challenge academic achievement of learners (Robinson, 2011).

Therefore, skilled, experienced and updated manpower have great significance on learners' academic performance, many schools have adopted strategies of increasing academic performance but the most important techniques they use is in service trainings. They organized and put into practice professional development in order to update and upgrade teachers' skills and knowledge. According to (Seton, 2005) asserted that ,professional development has positive significant relationship with teachers development and learners' academic performance. Professional

development is done systematically because it gives skills, knowledge, attitudes and values that employees are required to perform an assigned task in organization.

According to Olaniyan and Ojo (2008) staff training and professional development should always be done on mission and goals of staff, which also reflect the target of staff in future. This is because always every organization has an ambitions of growing and reaching as far as possible in future. So, no one can achieve this target without having professional and experienced staff which is well trained and expertize.

According to Nakpodia (2010), human resources development must undergo many different forms of professional development to make it perform better an assigned task. The findings indicated that there is difference between human resources development and learners' academic achievement. However, the researchers revealed that school personnel have to attend many trainings, seminars, workshops and other different professional development program which can sharpen, update and upgrade their knowledge and skills. And conclude that human resource experience, qualification and training has significant impact on learners' academic performance. teachers' perceptions on professional development was aligned with the standards of other kind of development that teachers can attend, teachers disclosed that collaboration, dialogue open discussion and learning about instructional facilities had a great impact on learning and teaching process. The similarity is that having training, other forms of professional development and having collaborative learning on instructional material plays great impact on learners' academic performance in any given schools around that world (Robinson,2011).

Most well-known staff professional development programs which are being provided in higher institutions are trainings, in service-teaching and being engaged in workshops, seminars and conferences among others (Ngala & Odebero, 2010). Continuous professional development teachers receive basic knowledge and skills such as classroom management skills, assessment techniques, development of teaching methodology and the techniques of mastering the contents. It was found out that teachers have good perceptions on in service training and its impacts on learners' academic performance and in classroom situation such assignment, group works, quizzes and exercises that are given in classroom. (Waheed, Salami, Ali, Dahlan, & Rahman, 2011). The study concluded that teachers' professional development has positive relationship with learners' academic performance and effective teaching.

In service teachers' education should be well designed, planned and implemented. Therefore, the main targeted can be contents development and methodology designing that are used to transmit the contents for improving teaching and learning process. Now & Lauer, (2005) noted that the contents of what teachers get from training is very important. They revealed that in service training emphasis on defined curricular resulted in much reform-oriented program than more general professional training but in reform oriented teachers' facilities was significantly relates with learners' achievement.

2.2. Teacher peer learning platforms and learners' academic performance

Peer learning is the transition of knowledge and skills by active facilitating and support among the people with same profession with the purpose of helping among so that common goal can be achieved together. Peer learning among the people of from the same social community, who needs to develop in their career or profession by helping each other to learn. This is termed learning by collaborating with peer groups (Topping & Ehly, 1998). On other side, the concept of peer assessment indicates the process done by learners to evaluate each other's work in group assigned tasks. According to Yusuf (2004) Indicated that, the conceptual of the new secondary school curriculum is targeted to empower the effective solving of the subject in the classroom by unprofessional teachers and inexperienced educators while developing knowledge and skills of teaching methods of the experienced teachers.

According to Zakaria, Chin, and Daud (2010) Asserted that the achievement of effective and efficient teaching and learning techniques, acquiring of skills and knowledge and skills must not emphasize on providing regulations, concepts, meaning and the procedures for learners to cram but it should be inclusive by engaging learners actively as primary beneficiary or participants. One of the best way to attain that, is peer learning which seems to be most emphasis on this study. Moreneo and Duran (2002) defined that peer learning as a method of collaborative learning based on the creation of pair of learners with a great relationship, that is, trainer and trainee who have not same academic capability but they share same goal. The objective can be attained through a relationship organized by the educators. Peer learning is treated as an excellent strategy for intermediating the mastery of group competences.

Fuchs, Mathes, and Martinez (2002), indicated that socialization knowledge, experience and skills acquired or occurred during peer learning process can give benefit to both sides of tutor and tutees by motivating the learners or teachers to study and augment their social status among the group.

Conducted research on assessment study and reported that peer learning developed learners' motivation to study. This finding is confirmed by Whitman (2012) and Annis (2013), who highlighted that peer learning might be the most intellectual compensation of a learner's profession. Many researchers revealed that peer teaching supported learners to perform better academically better than those who concentrate on reading materials for learning purposes.

The researcher like Topping (2010), Pointed that Peer learning acts as an effective method to develop self-esteem in learners. Peer learning helps collaboration among groups not only academically but also in community. One of the issues that attract public concern in most of the country is the gender stereotype in academic achievement of learners at schools.

With the highly increasing of students and the scarcity of resources, high augmentation of demands of teaching staff and others officials but peer learning can be solution on this kind of crisis in education system. In addition to that, this is giving chance to the teachers and students to take the responsibilities for their own development (Boud & Solomon, 2001) and (Ten & Durning, 2007).

Promoted collaboration is a support shared in same group members to help and motivate each other's through the activities of achieving the common vision and objective. This can be in terms of provision of feedback to increase performance or division of resources. Individual responsibility and personal accountability are the core to collaborative learning process. If members of association understand that they are chargeable and depend on one another to achieve the same goal then the level of being responsible in group is at great, this results into the increase of answerability (Torre et al., 2016; Johnson & Johnson, 2009 Johnson & Johnson, 2005).

Learning by cooperation assists learners to cognitively prepare and rearrange information, to integrate it into current knowledge and enhance holding of knowledge (Johnson et al., 1998).

Teachers' perception of their academic environment has a significant contribution on their learning and meaningful studying environment, which motivate togetherness amongst learners and constructive emotional area that promotes teach (Wayne et al., 2013). In peer learning this increase learning due to trusting correlation between peers.

Peer observation is defined as systematic lesson review process that puts together with a variety of different feedback sources such as feedback from students, evaluation outcomes, learners improvement and achievement. Byrne, Brown, and Challen (2000) pointed out that the objective of group observation can be treated as account for, developing the quality of teaching and learning with a target of developing academic learning. This strategy can be seen as a tool for assessing teaching performance and be utilized in performance appraisal of teacher. Teachers also needs sufficient time and help to express himself in teaching and visit one another's classrooms on weekly basis.

Teachers learn well from one another form the mistake which can be made by colleagues, by exchanging opinions with workmates from instructional educators and staff, and from making this over the course of their profession. This kind of school based teaching demands shift in school environment. It obliges to get support from skilled and experienced training from internal and outside. The findings are important according (Mednick, 2004). Davys, McKenna, and Tickle (2008) asserted that the aims of peer observation is to increase the quality of teaching and exchanging of good practices with workmates. Generally, it includes peer observation everyone 'practice with the purpose of developing practice and facilitating individual and professional development.

2.3. Teacher coaching and mentoring

Interactions and cooperation development relied on the attribution and understanding of those participants who are engaged in mentoring (Ambrosetti et al. 2014). Some of the researchers concluded that the meaning or definition of mentoring and coaching is not necessary. However, it has been confirmed that the term mentoring is empowered by the ways in which it is to be utilized and they are defined according to the context it intended to respond or depending on the users and the objective that he/she has (Jones & Brown 2011).

Mentoring is sometimes defined or explained as complex, according to (Heirdsfield et al. 2008) stated that it is defined as complex activities because it consists of such components as the relationship arise between the mentor and mentees, the desires and goals to be attained within the cooperation, as well as the context that that activities occurs in (Ambrosetti et al. 2014). In this respect, Kram's (1985) mentoring at Work first identified such crucial elements of the mentoring process. She holds that a mentoring relationship is founded on connection, needs and context.

Kram's (1985), mentioned at job firstly recognized such components of the mentoring process. The researcher discovered that mentoring cooperation is founded in interaction, desires and context. Thus, mentoring consists of three elements namely cooperation (the interaction between the mentor and mentees, progressive (where desires are recognized and the progression of these facilitate relationship), and context (for this level the context facilitates what will happen and how it occurs in the cooperation) (Lai, 2005). Confusion arises when one wants to define mentoring and ignore to include of the three components that are described above and to relate with the context it tends to be used in, the meaning which doesn't include both of the elements highlighted above do not reflect to maximize the potential of that word (Ambrosetti et al. 2014).

Many literature reviews in education career sometimes confuse mentoring and coaching approaches. Specifically, both approaches mentoring and coaching are related to professional development programs consisting one expert or instructor facilitating another in a mutually beneficial way. However, difference is that coaching directly relating to teaching and learning for academic achievement and it lasts short or medium period of time while mentoring is basically emphasize on learning for professional development and it can last medium or long period of time. Conclusively mentor can conduct the activity of coaching while coaches cannot not easily perform the activity of mentoring in any given organization. Globally, a mentee can be the one who can choose the mentor while in coaching organization unite a person who seems to be a desirable aching (Irby ,2012).

Mentoring and Coaching in the figures

Source:Reseacher (2022)

In teaching and learning activities mentoring is essential to the teachers because most new teachers and some of the teachers of English or other languages,even other subjects are not at the same level .

That is the reason why teachers need mentoring and coaching which always let them be updated and upgraded on educational change or reforms.

According to Lawy & Tedder (2011), indicate that there is no specific model of mentoring they continued expressing that if mentoring program are to effective and efficient, they must be in favor of mentees, flexible and modifiable to the mentees desires and situations. However, mentors training is all about or targeted to let them know the different possible theories that could be involved or and helping them to recognize and select form each theories and put the elements

necessary in every mentoring activity (Kadji-Beltran et al. 2013). Teachers could have mentors who can always facilitate them in teaching and learning activities. Mentors doesn't mean someone from external institutions or experts from outside but also mentoring can be done internally by director, director in charge of studies and senior teachers who are experienced in teaching and learning activities or who have been trained beforehand.

Mentoring must be defined depending on the nature of interaction: on one hand mentoring can be developmental when it is conducted in formative ways and has formative purpose and emphasize on individual or professional development, it must be professional oriented, suitable to the beneficiaries. On the other hands, mentoring can be performative when it is done in summative ways, means that it is conducted for judgement and assessing performance of any programs (Lawy & Tedder 2011; Tedder & Lawy 2009).

2.6.1. System's theory

The theory that the researchers used in this study is a system theory which described the input-output model. This theory was developed by theorist called Ludwig Von Bertalanffy in 1956. The theory, according to Koontz and Wehrich (cited in Martha 2005) noted that well organized firm cannot exist in a vacuum, it should always happen by basing on its system in which it is founded. They further continued to assess that input from the system are gained by an institution, which then change them into outputs. As it was done in this research, teachers are the inputs who have many training programs designed to them and they get professionalism through the activities of teaching and learning. Furthermore, the output in education perspective is related to students' academic performance.

However, the instructional facilities like laboratory, library, and computers labs are considered as resource inputs that contribute in teaching and learning activities in any given educational institution to achieve the desired goal. Robbins (Martha ,2005) indicated that an institution were highly explained as absorbers, processors and generators and as an institutional system could be described as is built up by many interconnecting factors. And the researchers furthermore described that any sudden change can affect many others subsystem in educational institutions.

2.4 Adult Learning Theory (Andragogy)

Starting from the definition of pedagogy as the starting concept, Knowles defined andragogy (adult learning theory) as “art and science of helping adults to learn” (1990, p.54). However, for understanding andragogy one have to start by understanding what is adult person? Therefore, in education perspective, Knowles (1970) asserted that there are at least two questions that can be answered for that types of questions: one, who has to be considered an adult person (social meaning)? And second which is self-character of an adults (psychological meaning)? Regarding to the first question adult is a person who has specific responsibilities such as parents, doctors and teachers while answers relating to the second question is an individual who became an adult psychologically at the level to which his/her status move from dependency to independent person, means that that one is not relying on others to live. It means that an adult "perceives herself or himself to be primarily responsible for her or his own life, actions and decisions" (Knowles, 1970, p. 24). Knowles pointed that the role of teachers in adults learning activities, asserted that teachers is the most important member of education system, and the teacher has big contribution in teaching and teaching environment (Knowles, 1970).

Therefore, researcher called Zepeda (2012) noted that continuous professional development has an adults learning activities which contribute to the students, teaching and administrative staff. Teachers’ continuous professional development is a type of adults learning that occurs while they are still fulfilling the duties at job, on workshops and training (Zepeda, Parylo, & Bengston, 2014). As responsible, teachers also must be provided responsibility of their own professional development. What motivate them? What do they like to study? What would they think about their needs? Letting teachers guessing what main target their professional development will empower in them, highly influence the performance of teachers in their experience to be lifelong students as adults (Trotter, 2006).

Andrology as it is considered as the model of adult learning process, indicated that adopting adults teaching program such as pre- experience, reflection, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and relationship should contribute to the augmentation of engagement reforms in teaching knowledge, belief and classroom management empowering teachers on how they can facilitate the activities of teaching and learning may find out the opportunity for the teachers to develop professional development principles practices (Weber-Mayrer, 2016). Other side, many research revealed that the most of the program for adults teachers did not involve adult learning program and they

consider them as they are new learners therefore educators cannot be satisfied with knowledge and skills that they could transfer in teaching program (Puteh, Kaliannan & Alam, 2015).

Schwandt and Tobin (1999) disclosed three basic program principles in pacification of adults' needs in development of staff programs. For the beginning they should be self-driven needs of adults, secondly, is that teachers utilize acquired knowledge and skills in practical ways, means that these programs must reflect what teachers learned while he/she is teaching in the classroom and finally, continuous professional development must give value the prior experience.

Many sources showed that educators have little or insufficient inputs in either the contents or format of their previous training (Karagiorgi et al., 2008). Several research by Kember, Kwan and Ledesma (2001) however the trainers viewed educators as adults' learners different from other kind of students, they always keep on training as the ways they treat them as good. For example Comings, Beder, Bingman, Reder and Smith (2003) pointed out that teachers explained that learners centered principles are more important for teachers, but sometimes some use teacher centered methods.

However, most of the instructors are accused that they used learners centered methods in their own collaboration with educators and their training is teachers centered and later they treat learners' active centered method like theories which are kept in documents not as teaching methods (Karagiorgi, et al., 2008).

In other hands, it is known that teachers are not agreed with the trainers' style of giving professional development, format of the contents instead of real staff professional development. As the results of that inefficient teaching methods used by trainers, much of teachers do not get the most important information as long as they are not included in the process of decision making one of the researcher disclosed that "disjunction of learning and teaching styles" and "apparent irrelevance of the learning activity" as two reasons that can attribute to resistance to learning (Brookfield, 1990).

Precisely, provision of continuous professional development is the main target of all educational organizations, there are many researches and studies on the effective continuous professional development. However, this theory is considered as quiet potential and important to the school administrators who have other responsibility to perform, but it is only taking little hour which was

designed to the adults learning and education into consideration. Teachers' continuous professional development can become more effective (Beavers, 2009). Study analyzed adults learning programs and teachers' professional development and then revealed that teachers have to cooperate with workmates, interact with others from other institutions and study things which can be utilized in his/ her classroom activities (Trotter, 2006).

Creating such conducive environment which offer the teachers an opportunity of sharing ideas, experience, brainstorming and discussion. And then considering teachers as a focal point of adults learners are the most important factors of effective continuous professional development for educators. There are many theories which explained professional development. Unfortunately, many educational institutions are not strived to implement these strategies because of a lot of tasks and other financial means which become a barrier. However, according to Beavers (2009) inserting adults learning in education system had significant influence on learners' academic performance.

2.5 The Training Model

Training model is well known academically around the world and has been an important instrument that all the instructors and administrative staff used transmitting continuous professional development (Little, 1994; Kelly & McDiarmid, 2002).

This model develops a capability of teacher which gives teachers the opportunities of improving their skills, knowledge which lead them to demonstrate their competences. Around the world, continuous professional development is provided by the experts in education curriculum and methodology and the program of this professional development is always known by the experts. Teachers are seen as passive elements while conducting this professional training.

In general training it is provided in the way which is different from other professional activities and it is comprised by experts in education who are in addition to that outsider from the school (Burbank & Kauchak, 2003). Training can take place out of the schools of participated teachers because when it is provided in the interior place where trainees' works, the training are criticized for not being standard or effective. (Kennedy, 2005). Training model has an implication which means that teaching and administrative staffs must have additional skills and knowledge which increase their experience and expertise.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used quantitative and qualitative approaches. Descriptive research design was utilized to study significant relationship between independent variable which is teachers' continuous professional development and dependent variable which is learners' academic performance. This study used 9 head teachers, 5 deputy head teachers in charge of studies, and 144 teachers both are from two sectors Tumba and Kinyira sectors primary schools. The researchers decide to use this kind of people because of their responsibilities, which have relationship with teachers' continuous professional development and learners' academic performance. Therefore, total population of the study is 158 people. This study used both probability and non-probability sampling.

Data collection instruments are the tools that the researcher used to collect the information from the respondents. There are many instruments but the researcher tried to select some of them which are relevant to the problem study "relationship between teachers' continuous professional development and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools" those are: Questionnaire is an instruments which is commonly used in social sciences while conducting quantitative data, it is very useful when the researcher wants to collect data from big number of respondents (Omari, 2011). The researcher sent the questionnaire to the teachers, directors and directors in charge of studies to fill their information which are relevant to the questions asked. Interview will be used in collecting qualitative data from head teachers, director in charge of studies. Interview was also used, it refers to the oral communication between interviewee and interviewer and the answers should be answered in verbal ways of exchanging information (Kothari, 2004).

Quantitative was used on closed ended questions where the respondents have choices among many alternative while qualitative analysis used an open ended question which gave the respondents the chance to give his/her opinions. Descriptive statistic was utilized to make summary of quantifiable data. Data processing used SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences). Percentage, mean and standard deviation was used in the data interpretation. The study used Cronbach alpha to test the consistence of the questionnaire which was used during the period of data collection.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Teacher in-service training and learners' academic performance

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
School-based training improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2212	.83168
BLF-provided training improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1593	.94080
British Council-provided training affect learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.0265	1.16082
Training incentives improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.4071	.78646
Training attendance improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.5752	.65199
Training assessments improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2035	.83623
Post-training follow-ups improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2655	.90650
English proficiency tests improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.0442	.94858
Training duration improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.0531	1.11676
Training frequency improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1770	.86839
Overall Mean	113			4.2132	0.90482

Note: Strongly Disagree = [1] = Very Low mean; Disagree= [1-2] =Low mean; Neutral= [2-3] =moderated mean; Agree= [3-4] =High mean; Strongly Agree= [4-5] = Very High mean

The findings from table 3, indicated that majority of respondents strongly agreed that the following factors influence learners’ academic performance. They are namely: School-based training improves learners’ academic performance($\mu=4.2212$ and $STD=.83168$), BLF-provided training improves learners’ academic performance($\mu=4.1593$ and $STD=.94080$), British Council-provided training affect learners’ academic performance($\mu=4.0265$ and $STD=1.16082$), Training incentives improve learners academic performance($\mu=4.4071$ and $STD=.78646$), Training attendance improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.5752$ and $STD=.65199$), Training assessments improve learners academic performance($\mu=4.2035$ and $STD=.83623$), Post-training follow-ups improve learners academic performance($\mu=4.2655$ and $STD=.90650$), English proficiency tests improve learners academic performance($\mu=4.0442$ and $STD=.94858$), Training duration improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.0531$ and $STD=1.11676$), Training frequency improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.1770$ and $STD=.86839$). The overall, decision is that most of respondents had strongly agree that Teacher in-service training affect and learners’ academic performance as shown by ($\mu= 4.2132$ and $STD= 0.90482$).

The findings from interview indicated that most of the respondents approved that teachers in-service training increase learners’ academic performance because they get new knowledge and skills while they are still in their career without letting them quit the professionalism this is an important factor which influence learners’ achievement.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Teacher peer learning platforms

N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
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Regular one to one peer support improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.3186	.71045
Occasional one to one peer support improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.4602	.85602
Community of Practice Meetings improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2743	.89889
Peer lesson observation improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.3805	.78284
Peer feedback improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2832	.86053
Out-of-school study trips improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2743	.88890
Teacher group study improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1416	.92454
Borrowing teaching aids from a peer improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.3097	.79147
Using English with colleagues improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.5487	.76755
Peer imitation improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1593	.99612
Overall mean	113			4.3150	0.84773

Note: Strongly Disagree = [1] = Very Low mean; Disagree= [1-2] =Low mean; Neutral= [2-3] =moderated mean; Agree= [3-4] =High mean; Strongly Agree= [4-5] = Very High mean

The findings from table 4, showed that the majority of respondents approved that the following variables affect learners academic performance as they follow: Regular one to one peer support improves learners’ academic performance($\mu=4.3186$ and $STD=.71045$), Occasional one to one peer support improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.4602$ and $STD=.85602$), Community of Practice Meetings improve learners academic performance($\mu=4.2743$ and $STD=.89889$), Peer lesson observation improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.3805$ and $STD=.78284$), Peer feedback improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.2832$ and $STD=.86053$), Out-of-school study trips improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.2743$ and $STD=.88890$), Teacher group study improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.1416$ and $STD=.92454$), Borrowing teaching aids from a peer improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.3097$ and $STD=.79147$), Using English with colleagues improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.5487$ and $STD=.76755$), Peer imitation improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.1593$ and $STD=.99612$). The overall, decision is that most of respondents had strongly agree that Teacher peer learning platforms affect and learners’ academic performance as shown by ($\mu= 4.3150$ and $STD= 0.84773$).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Teacher coaching and mentoring

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
SBM mentoring improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2478	.78525

SSL mentoring improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2212	.72868
Headteacher's observation improves learners' academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2478	.75037
REB mentors improve learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1947	.92445
SLF guidance and coaching improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1858	.85093
SEI supervision improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.1858	.77400
Teacher private mentor improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2212	1.02412
Teacher online mentoring improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.2832	.77309
Tutorship improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.3009	.81158
Coaching and mentoring of new teachers by school leaders improves learners academic performance	113	1.00	5.00	4.3009	.81158
Overall mean	113			4.2389	0.82340

Note: Strongly Disagree = [1] = Very Low mean; Disagree= [1-2] =Low mean; Neutral= [2-3] =moderated mean; Agree= [3-4] =High mean; Strongly Agree= [4-5] = Very High mean

The outcome from table 5, revealed that most of the respondents strongly agreed that the following variable influence learners' academic performance. They are namely: SBM mentoring improves learners' academic performance($\mu=4.2478$ and $STD=.78525$), SSL mentoring improves learners' academic performance($\mu=4.2212$ and $STD=.72868$), Head teacher's observation improves learners' academic performance($\mu=4.2478$ and $STD=.75037$), REB mentors improve learners'

academic performance($\mu=4.1947$ and $STD=.92445$), SLF guidance and coaching improves learners' academic performance($\mu=4.1858$ and $STD=.85093$), SEI supervision improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.2212$ and $STD=1.02412$), Teacher private mentor improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.2832$ and $STD=.77309$), Teacher online mentoring improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.2832$ and $STD=.77309$), Tutorship improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.3009$ and $STD=.81158$), Coaching and mentoring of new teachers by school leaders improves learners academic performance($\mu=4.3009$ and $STD=.81158$). The overall, decision is that most of respondents had strongly agree that Teacher coaching and mentoring affect and learners' academic performance as shown by ($\mu= 4.2389$ and $STD= 0.82340$).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for learners' academic performance

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
The rate of learners' success in district test has increased in last five years	113	1.00	5.00	4.2743	.85824
Students motivation increased in the School's internal exams in the last five years	113	1.00	5.00	4.3894	.74921
Appreciation from local community and administration about learning process increased in last five years	113	1.00	5.00	4.2478	.92129
The number of learners getting the second seating exams decreased in the last 5 years	113	1.00	5.00	4.3894	.71256
The number of Students active participants and open during teaching-learning process increased in the last 5 years	113	1.00	5.00	4.2743	.77053
Numbers of learners who got discouraged or the drop out decreased in the last five Years.	113	1.00	5.00	4.5221	.78031

Concentration of students has been increased in this last five years	113	1.00	5.00	4.4159	.72857
The time management, Attendance, Discipline and the number of students having free revision increased in the last 5 Years.	113	1.00	5.00	3.8230	1.10381
The number of learners unclassified in national exams were reduced in this last five years	113	1.00	5.00	4.0531	.89483
The number of learners who get high grade in national exams increased in last five years.	113	1.00	5.00	4.0177	1.05206
Overall mean	113			4.2407	0.85714

Note: Strongly Disagree = [1] = Very Low mean; Disagree= [1-2] =Low mean; Neutral= [2-3] =moderated mean; Agree= [3-4] =High mean; Strongly Agree= [4-5] = Very High mean

The outcome from table 6, showed that the majority of respondents strongly that academic performance had been increased in last five years as they are indicated by the following variables: The rate of learners' success in district test has increased in last five years($\mu=4.2743$ and $STD=.85824$), Students motivation increased in the School's internal exams in the last five years($\mu=4.3894$ and $STD=.74921$), Appreciation from local community and administration about learning process increased in last five years($\mu=4.2478$ and $STD=.92129$), The number of learners getting the second seating exams decreased in the last 5 years($\mu=4.3894$ and $STD=.71256$), The number of Students active participants and open during teaching-learning process increased in the last 5 years($\mu=4.2743$ and $STD=.77053$), The number of Students active participants and open during teaching-learning process increased in the last 5 years($\mu=4.5221$ and $STD=.78031$), Numbers of learners who got discouraged or the drop out decreased in the last five Years($\mu=4.4159$ and $STD=.72857$), Concentration of students has been increased in this last five years($\mu=4.4159$ and $STD=.72857$), The time management, Attendance, Discipline and the number of students having free revision increased in the last 5 Years($\mu=3.8230$ and $STD=1.10381$), The number of learners unclassified in national exams were reduced in this last five years($\mu=4.0531$ and

STD=.89483), The number of learners who get high grade in national exams increased in last five years($\mu=4.0177$ and $STD=1.05206$). The overall, decision is that most of respondents had strongly agree that learners' academic performance increased as shown by ($\mu= 4.2389$ and $STD= 0.82340$).

4.3. Discussion of findings

4.3.1. Interpretation of findings using correlation analysis

Table 5: Model Summary on teacher in service training

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.870 ^a	.756	.726	.11253

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers in service training

The results in table 7, indicated that 75.6 % of the variation in dependent variables (learners academic performance can be explained by for teacher in service training. The remaining percentage can be attributed to other variables which are not mentioned in this model.

Table 6: The analysis of variance on teacher in service training

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.315	1	.315	24.838	.001 ^b
	Residual	.101	8	.013		

Total .416 9

a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher in service training

The results from variance analysis in table 8, indicated regression coefficient as showed in table. There is significant effect (P value >0.05). Conclusively there is significant effect of teacher in service training on learners' academic performance. Then, null hypothesis is rejected while alternative is accepted.

Table 7: Regression coefficients for teachers in service training on learners' academic performance

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.351	.922		-.381	.713
Teacher in-service training	1.090	.219	.870	4.984	.001

a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

The results from table 9, indicated that there was a positive and significant effect of teachers in service training on learners academic performance (B=0.870, P value >0.01). This explains that one unit of change in teachers' in-service training, increases learners academic performance by 1.090 units, this results corroborates with (Harindintwari, et al 2020) where revealed that human resource availability contribute to school materials utilization .

Table 8: Model Summary for teachers' peer learning and learners' academic performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.894 ^a	.800	.775		.10204

a. Predictors: (Constant), teachers peer learning

The results in table 10, indicated that 80.0 % of the variation in dependent variables, learners' academic performance can be explained by for teacher peer learning the remaining percentage can be attributed to other variables which are not mentioned in this model.

Table 9: The analysis of variance on teachers' peer learning and learners' academic performance.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.333	1	.333	31.936	.000 ^b
	Residual	.083	8	.010		
	Total	.416	9			

a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), teachers peer learning

The results from variance analysis in table 11, indicated regression coefficient as showed in table there is significant effect (P value >0.05). Conclusively there is significant effect of teacher peer learning on learners' academic performance. Then, null hypothesis is rejected while alternative is accepted.

Table 10: Regression coefficients for teachers coaching and learners' academic performance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-2.441	1.183		-2.064	.073
	teachers peer learning	1.549	.274	.894	5.651	.000

a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

The results from table 12, indicated that there was a positive and significant effect of teachers' peer learning on learners' academic performance (B=0.894, P value >0.00). This explains that one unit of change in teachers' peer learning, increases learners' academic performance by 1.549 units.

Table 11: Model Summary for teachers coaching and mentoring

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.902 ^a	.814	.791	.09834

a. Predictors: (Constant), teachers coaching and mentoring

The results in table 13, indicated that 81.4 % of the variation in dependent variables (learners' academic performance) can be explained by for teachers coaching and mentoring the remaining percentage can be attributed to other variables which are not mentioned in this model.

Table 12: The analysis of variance on teachers coaching and mentoring on learners' academic performance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.338	1	.338	34.993	.000 ^b
	Residual	.077	8	.010		
	Total	.416	9			

a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), teachers coaching and mentoring

The results from variance analysis in table 14, indicated regression coefficient as showed in table there is significance effect (P value >0.05). Conclusively there is significant effect of teacher coaching and mentoring on learners' academic performance. Then, null hypothesis is rejected while alternative is accepted.

Table 13: Regression coefficients for teachers coaching and mentoring and learners' academic performance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	14.125	3.105		-4.549	.002

Teachers coaching and mentoring	4.333	.732	.902	5.915	.000
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a. Dependent Variable: academic performance

The results from table 15, indicated that there was a positive and significant effect of teachers coaching and mentoring on learners' academic performance (B=0.902, P value >0.00). This explains that one unit of change in teachers coaching and mentoring, increases learners' academic performance by 4.333 units.

CONCLUSION

The findings from the objective to Examine the relationship between Teacher in-service training and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools, the results indicated that there is positive and significant effect of teacher in service training on learners' academic performance (B=0.870, P value >0.01). Means that null of hypotheses was rejected and alternative hypotheses were accepted. This was achieved by providing 10 statements or options about teachers in service training for which the respondents were asked to choose appropriate box by Likert scales. Therefore, it was found that teachers in service training variables have effect with overall mean and standard deviation ($\mu = 4.2132$ and $STD = 0.90482$).

The findings from the objective which is to explore the relationship between Teacher peer learning platforms and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools, the results indicated that there is positive and significant effect of Teacher peer learning platforms on learners academic performance (B=0.894, P value >0.00). Means that null of hypotheses was rejected and alternative hypotheses were accepted. This was achieved by providing 10 statements or options about Teacher peer learning platforms for which the respondents were asked to choose appropriate box by Likert scales. Therefore, it was found that Teacher peer learning platforms variables have effect with overall mean and standard deviation ($\mu = 4.3150$ and $STD = 0.84773$).

The findings from the objective which is to Analyze the relationship between teacher coaching and mentoring and learners' academic performance in Rulindo primary schools, the results indicated that there is positive and significant effect of teacher coaching and mentoring on learners'

academic performance ($B=0.894$, P value >0.00). This finding collaborates with the results of Harindintwari et al (2020) where he stated that human resource is very crucial for student performance. Means that null of hypotheses was rejected and alternative hypotheses were accepted. This was achieved by providing 10 statements or options about teacher coaching and mentoring for which the respondents were asked to choose appropriate box by Likert scales. Therefore, it was found that teacher coaching and mentoring variables have effect with overall mean and standard deviation ($\mu= 4.3150$ and $STD= 0.84773$).

Recommendations

Basing the findings from the study the researcher revealed that there are some gaps which needs to be solved by different organs such as Rwanda Education Board, Non-governmental Organizations across the world. They are namely:

REB should provide frequent continuous professional development in schools across the country.

REB should make survey on how continuous professional development that they have provided is impacting the quality of education.

Stakeholders must invest their money in giving continuous professional development to teaching and administrative staff.

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